

Average Energy as a Deterministic Attribute Due to Statistics of $\exp(ipx)$

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A quantum particle (or photon) is described by the two dimensional probabilistic $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, with t and x being treated as independent. $\exp(-iEt)$ suggests a stochasticity in time associated with energy E , but none in space. Similarly, there is a stochasticity in x associated with p but none in time. For $-Et+px$ to be invariant as seen in different frames moving with constant average velocities, $-EE+pp$ must also be an invariant i.e. equal momo ($c=1$). This leads to a contradiction. $\exp(ipx)$ suggests a stochasticity in x for a given p , but $-EE+pp=momom$ converts a given p into an E , so there exists stochasticity in x for E as well (which contracts the notion that $\exp(-iEt)$ is only stochastic in time). The link between E and p , however, which breaks $x-t$ independence is the notion of average velocity $v=x/t$, which is physical (as is $\exp(ipx)$). How does one deal with this contradiction?

We suggest that p and E are associated with different physical interaction processes. P is related to impulse hits, while E may be associated with loss of energy over a distance if a potential $V(x)$ exists. Even though $\exp(ipx)$ suggests stochasticity in x , at the same time one considers fixed objects (targets, slits) and even potentials $V(x)$ at well-defined deterministic x points. This seems to mean that if one wishes to make energy deterministic at each x , one must create an average of $\exp(ipx)$ s.

We argue that there seem to be two important ideas associated with $\exp(ipx)$. First, it is a two-dimensional probability linked to a flux because it is due to p which is due to a v . Probability flux does not get created or destroyed (unless there are sinks or sources). This leads to issues when dealing with a bound state which should be localized. A flux probability is not localized, nor is an average in general (except in the case of an infinite potential). A bound state problem is really a flux problem consisting of a particle trapped in a potential together with it tunneling out or in i.e. one has a dynamic equilibrium picture somewhat like evaporation in equilibrium. (To see the clear difference between a state based probability and a flux-based one, consider the problem of a photon moving in the x direction and reflecting/refracting from an n_1-n_2 (index of refraction) y -plane at $x=0$. State probabilities ($P(\text{reflect})$, $P(\text{refract})$) are not sufficient to solve the problem, but a flux-based one $\exp(ipx)$ which allows a single particle to appear as if in a steady stream scenario is.)

Secondly, unlike evaporation, the guiding statistical condition for $\exp(ipx)$ is that its average makes E deterministic in x space. Thus E is like T (temperature) in that it is a statistical parameter, but it is not based on maximization of entropy (equilibration), but rather in creating E as an average which is then treated as deterministic (ignoring in a sense $\exp(-iEt)$ value characterizing an equilibrium system (not based on equilibration). This deterministic E system is linked with discrete values (due to the $\exp(ipx)$ equilibrium), but given that E is treated as deterministic, a stochastic process based on maximization of entropy is introduced to describe the absorption and emission of photons (which allow for jumps from one average-deterministic E_n to another).

We argue that the flux-like probability $\exp(ipx)$ exists in order to deal with sharp interfaces (e.g. n_1-n_2 index of refraction) at a deterministic $x=0$ which probabilistically leads to different p values. It uses the reverse approach i.e. a deterministic p and a stochastic x . In such a way, one

may use continuity (and first derivative continuity) at the sharp x with flux-probabilities containing the various allowed p values (due to the impulses). The continuity follows from no sinks or sources existing for the flux-like probability.

Statistical Principle Other Than Maximization of Entropy

In classical mechanics, there exists the notion of determinism. When tossing a coin or die, there is the notion of probability as one does not know the outcome. We argue that the possible states of the coin or die are deterministic i.e. the coin is either a head or tail etc. Thus the tossing or rolling process becomes the stochastic process and one uses the idea of maximum entropy subject to constraints to show that one has no idea what result occurs. The idea of maximum entropy is one which is linked to probabilities when there is no biased information, or only bias based on a constraint, e.g. average energy.

We suggest, however, that another statistical principle exists, namely one in which a stochastic probability creates an average value which is treated as deterministic. This principle is directly linked with motion and so is associated with flux like probabilities which are different from the usual state probabilities i.e. $P(\text{heads})$, $P(\text{tails})$. This principle links $\exp(ipx)$ s to a constant, statistical E (energy), but comes with the consequences of a flux, steady stream picture.

Flux Probabilities Associated with Motion

One usually thinks in terms of probabilities of a state i.e. a die shows a certain number, a coin is heads or tails. For a photon moving in the x direction and reflecting/refracting at $x=0$ (interface of n_1 - n_2 indices of refraction along the y axis), the states are "reflected" and "refracted" and so one may assign probabilities to these. As we have argued before, such probabilities do not allow for the solution of this reflection-refraction problem. Rather one requires a flux related probability $\exp(ipx)$ which we argue may follow from maximizing Shannon's entropy $P(x)\ln(P(x))$ subject to the periodic constraint $i \int p(x) P(x) dx$ where p is the Lagrange multiplier. Thus p is like a statistical average value associated with stochasticity in x i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. Similarly, for a free particle, one has $\exp(-iEt)$. This approach treats x and t as independent, but physically the average $v=x/t$ must also exist. Multiplying $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ suggests that the phase should be invariant as seen from different frames moving at constant average v . This implies that:

$-E + pv$ must also be an invariant i.e. $-E + pv = \text{const}$ ($c=1$) ((1))

((1)) however, leads to a contradiction. $\exp(-iEt)$ suggests that E only leads to stochasticity in time. $\exp(ipx)$ suggests there is stochasticity in space associated with p . ((1)), however, links a p to an E , so there is stochasticity of E in space. This leads to issues if one associates p with an impulse hit and E with a loss/gain in energy as a particle moves through a potential $V(x)$. In such a case, E is deterministically known at each x . In other words, even though $\exp(ipx)$ suggests stochasticity in x , at the same time there exists determinism in x through $V(x)$ or through objects such as the n_1 - n_2 interface or a target or an n -slit apparatus which exist at precise x

positions. How may one reconcile a stochastic x view associated with p with determinism in x ? We suggest one must create averages of $\exp(ipx)$ s so that these may be treated as deterministic. We argue there exists a statistical principle, namely that in certain cases probabilities may combine to create deterministic-like averages, at least in a certain dimension. In order to create determinism in x for energy E , due to $V(x)$ one needs an average kinetic energy:

$$KE(x) = \left\{ \sum_{p} a(p) \exp(ipx) p^2 / 2m \right\} / \left\{ \sum_{p} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} \quad ((2))$$

$KE(x)$ when added to $V(x)$ yields E a constant at all x . We suggest that E is like T , temperature, in classical statistical mechanics, except for the fact that it is based on a different driving principle. Temperature follows from maximizing entropy subject to a constraint on average energy, with e_i (single particle energy) being a deterministic state of a single particle. Stochasticity enters through changes from one deterministic state to another. E , on the other hand, follows from an average kinetic energy representing a deterministic-like value. One creates an average-deterministic E state of a system with a potential $V(x)$. Due to the form $\exp(ipx)$, only discrete E values hold. This is also due to the boundary condition, which we discuss next.

Flux-Like Probabilities

We argued above that $\exp(ipx)$ is a flux-like probability meaning it is associated with motion and exists in all of space. This is very different from the state based probabilities i.e. $P(\text{heads})$, $P(\text{tails})$. If there are no sinks or sources for probability, even though $\exp(ipx)$ represents stochasticity in x , and there exist sharp- x constraints (potential, n_1 - n_2 interfaces), $\exp(ipx)$ may be used to deal with this. (In a later section we link the stochasticity of x and deterministic value of p in $\exp(ipx)$ to the deterministic value of the sharp- x and the probabilistic p values which may result from impulses).

We argue that a flux-like probability exists so that a single particle (e.g. a photon) may have the same probabilistic features as a steady stream (which is also flux-based). A flux-like probability associated with continuity at x and equal d/dx at x (equivalent to flux-like probability conservation and p probability conservation) may solve the one dimensional photon reflection-refraction problem, while state probabilities $P(\text{reflected})$, $P(\text{refracted})$ cannot.

What happens when one considers flux-like probabilities in a bound state problem with $V(x)$? In the classical statistical mechanical case of a gas, one may have a container at a temperature T so that stochastic (maximum entropy) collisions within the gas are the same as those with the wall. At the same time, the canonical assumption (fixed average energy), allows for nonzero probability for high single particle energies and gives rise to evaporated particles (if there is an opening in the container) which may come into equilibrium with the bound particles.

In the quantum case, one has a flux-probability and so there is no notion of particles being localized within a region of space (between classical turning points) except in the case of an infinite potential. Like in the canonical situation, all $\exp(ipx)$ s (i.e. all p values) are included, but these exist everywhere in space. The problem is a combined equilibrium of a bound particle and particle which has tunneled out or is trying to tunnel in.

Using $\exp(ipx)$ s to form an average already creates an equilibrium with bound and no-bound (tunneled) probabilities. This flux-like probability $\exp(ipx)$ is used to create a deterministic $KE(x)$ instead of obeying maximum entropy. $\langle \exp(ipx) \rangle$ represents a statistical quantity linked with $V(x)$ (summed) to create the statistical E at all x points (within the turning points and without).

The inherent flux-like nature of $\exp(ipx)$ (which is further discussed in the next section) becomes associated with $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. $W^*(x)W(x)$ yields a state probability $P(x)$ and $a^*(p)a(p)$ a state probability $P(p)$. These appear in the literature (1) in spatial and momentum Shannon entropy expressions associated with an energy state n , but we argue that they are associated with a kind of equilibrium between a tunneled particle and a bound one. For $W(x)W(x)$, the bound particle exists within the classical turning points and the tunneled one outside. $-W(x)W(x) \ln\{W(x)W(x)\}$ is the spatial Shannon's entropy and so entropy adds for the two regions i.e. $S(\text{within classical turning points}) + S(\text{tunneled}) = S(\text{total spatial})$.

By using probability $\exp(ipx)$ to create an average system E , one treats it as a deterministic value, ignoring in the sense the time stochasticity in $\exp(-iEt)$. If one has deterministic states (as in the case of a coin, die or single particle energy in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas), one may consider a stochastic process based on maximum entropy which governs the probabilities associated with these deterministic states. Thus the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor is used even in quantum mechanics when applied to deterministic single particle energy states. The Maxwell-Boltzmann factor is the result of maximization of entropy subject to a real constraint. We suggest that in the next section that a flux-like probability is also maximization of entropy linked to state variables (but for different reasons) subject to a periodic constraint (using i) which makes it exist in all of space.

Flux-Like Probability and States

The flux-like probability $\exp(ipx)$ is a function of two state variables, p and x . It is a flux-like probability because it repeats itself in space periodically. The form $\exp(ipx)$ represents a known or deterministic type p (although this may be an average) and an x which is stochastic. Why does such a flux-like probability exist? We argue that one may have problems in which there is a sharp change, say an index of refraction of $n_1=1$ changing to $n_2>n_1$ at $x=0$. This leads to impulse hits and momentum changes linked with probabilities. At a specific deterministic x , one has probability linked with changing p . If these probabilities are somehow linked to the change in index of refraction (and not some inherent stochastic mechanism at the boundary which creates reflected and refracted photons), one may account for such a scenario by applying the reverse situation, we argue.

In particular, changing p values (due to impulses) associated with probability at a deterministic x ($x=0$), may be switched to a stochastic x with a deterministic p . In such a case, one has a probability which is a function of p, x with x being the stochastic variable. If there are no sources and sinks, such a probability's continuity and momentum continuity (linked to impulses) allows for a built-in way to adjust to sharp changes at say an $x=0$ point. E, in the reflection-refraction case and others does not change, suggesting a kind of inherent smooth motion $\exp(-iEt)$.

This still does not conclusively determine this flux-like probability form. As previously noted, we use the maximization of Shannon's entropy $-P(x)\ln(P(x))$ subject to a periodic constraint $i px$

$P(x)$. The periodic constraint leads to a two dimensional probability and yields the flux-like nature. “ p ” is the Lagrange multiplier (implying a kind of average) and x is the stochastic variable.

This approach lends itself to the solution of a photon moving in the x direction which encounters an n_1 - n_2 interface (y axis) at $x=0$. It also appears for a non-infinite square well. Inside the well one has an average Sum of $p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and outside a different one. One may match these at $x=a$ (well edge) as well as the first derivative. Both of these average functions are linked with the same E as in the incident, reflected, refracted situation. Thus the discontinuity at a sharp x value (linked with impulses) with no E change may be dealt with by using the $\exp(ipx)$ form (average over various $\exp(ipx)$ s).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there are two kinds of probabilities, state based and flux-based, which are linked with different kinds of statistical rules. State based probabilities tend to be linked with maximization of entropy subject to a constraint(s) and the states are considered to be deterministic i.e. not stochastic. In particular, the stochasticity associated with the maximization of entropy is linked with changing from one state to another, e.g. e_i (single particle energy state). This e_i appears in the constraint.

A flux-based probability is two-dimensional and periodic and is linked with motion in space or time $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-iEt)$. The flux-based probability exists in all space (or time) and so is linked with steady state like motion which may be applied to a single particle. The notion of a flux-based probability becomes clear when one considers a photon moving in the x direction which reflects-refracts from an n_1 - n_2 (indices of refraction) interface along the y axis at $x=0$. State based probabilities, i.e. $P(\text{reflect})$, $P(\text{refract})$, do not solve the problem, but a flux-based probability $\exp(ipx)$ does (imposing continuity of the probability and its derivative i.e. conservation of flux based probability and average momentum in space).

A flux-based probability $\exp(ipx)$ may also be obtained by maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to a periodic constraint, i.e. one which uses i . This makes the probability flux-based. The nature of this probability is different. One may have E constant, but impulse hits occur with some probability at a sharp x . One may use the reverse scenario, i.e. a probabilistic x with a deterministic p to construct a flux-like probability. Then continuity using the various allowed p values set to the fixed x allows one to solve the problem as in the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem. The probability $\exp(ipx)$ is still based on maximization of entropy, but the scenario is different from say $\exp(-e_i/T)$. E_i is the variable which changes in a collision and T (temperature) the Lagrange multiplier. For $\exp(ipx)$, x is the stochastic variable, but it is p , the Lagrange multiplier which will change in an interaction. One needs to know these possible changes from the mechanics of the problem (i.e. reflection-refraction or n -slits). The allowed p values due to the impulse in a sense are deterministic.

In the case of p and E , we argue that E is stochastic in time and p in space. If $\exp(ipx-iEt)$, however, is invariant as seen from a frame moving at a constant average v the notion of average $v=x/t$ breaks the independence of x and t . If $-Et+px$ is invariant, then so is $-EE+pp = \text{momo}$ ($c=1$). This means that a given p corresponds to an E . A given p , however, implies stochasticity in x , $\exp(ipx)$, so E is also stochastic in x . This is a problem if one wishes to think of

E (kinetic energy) as a quantity which may change with x due to a potential $V(x)$. In order to create a $KE(x)$, i.e. a deterministic value, it seems one must create an average using $\exp(ipx)$ s. These flux type probabilities create a $KE(x)$ which when added to $V(x)$ creates the statistical constant E (like Temperature), but not based on maximization of entropy. Given that $\exp(ipx)$ is a flux based probability, this probability exists everywhere, so a bound state problem cannot confine a particle to a region between classical turning points. Rather, one has an equilibrium of a bound particle and tunneled particle, which is in keeping with the notion of flux. The statistical value of E , although associated with stochasticity in time $\exp(-iEt)$, is taken to represent a deterministic state. Thus, one may think in terms of a deterministic probability in E , i.e. $P(E_n)$ (n =state) and consider maximization of entropy as linked with a process which moves the particle from one E_n state to another.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box